

Subject IDs in ADNI dataset (434 subjects)

No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage	No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage	No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage
1	002_S_5018	AD	44	116_S_4732	AD	87	012_S_4012	MCI
2	006_S_4153	AD	45	123_S_4526	AD	88	012_S_4128	MCI
3	006_S_4192	AD	46	128_S_4772	AD	89	012_S_4188	MCI
4	006_S_4546	AD	47	128_S_4774	AD	90	012_S_4849	MCI
5	006_S_4867	AD	48	128_S_5123	AD	91	012_S_4987	MCI
6	009_S_5027	AD	49	130_S_4589	AD	92	013_S_2324	MCI
7	009_S_5037	AD	50	130_S_4641	AD	93	013_S_2389	MCI
8	009_S_5252	AD	51	130_S_4660	AD	94	013_S_4268	MCI
9	011_S_4827	AD	52	130_S_4730	AD	95	013_S_4791	MCI
10	011_S_4845	AD	53	130_S_4971	AD	96	013_S_4917	MCI
11	011_S_4912	AD	54	130_S_4982	AD	97	014_S_2185	MCI
12	011_S_4949	AD	55	130_S_4984	AD	98	014_S_2308	MCI
13	013_S_5071	AD	56	130_S_5006	AD	99	014_S_4328	MCI
14	014_S_4039	AD	57	130_S_5059	AD	100	016_S_5031	MCI
15	014_S_4615	AD	58	135_S_4657	AD	101	018_S_2133	MCI
16	018_S_4696	AD	59	135_S_4676	AD	102	018_S_2138	MCI
17	018_S_4733	AD	60	135_S_4863	AD	103	018_S_2155	MCI
18	019_S_4252	AD	61	035_S_4954	AD	104	018_S_2180	MCI
19	019_S_4477	AD	62	135_S_5015	AD	105	018_S_4597	MCI
20	019_S_4549	AD	63	137_S_4211	AD	106	018_S_4809	MCI
21	019_S_5012	AD	64	137_S_4258	AD	107	018_S_4868	MCI
22	019_S_5019	AD	65	137_S_4672	AD	108	019_S_4285	MCI
23	023_S_4501	AD	66	137_S_4756	AD	109	019_S_4680	MCI
24	024_S_4223	AD	67	153_S_4172	AD	110	023_S_2068	MCI
25	024_S_4280	AD	68	002_S_2010	MCI	111	023_S_4241	MCI
26	024_S_4905	AD	69	002_S_2043	MCI	112	024_S_2239	MCI
27	024_S_5054	AD	70	002_S_2073	MCI	113	024_S_4392	MCI
28	031_S_4024	AD	71	002_S_4237	MCI	114	024_S_4674	MCI
29	033_S_5013	AD	72	002_S_4447	MCI	115	031_S_2018	MCI
30	033_S_5017	AD	73	002_S_4473	MCI	116	031_S_2022	MCI
31	033_S_5087	AD	74	002_S_4799	MCI	117	031_S_2233	MCI
32	036_S_4820	AD	75	006_S_4679	MCI	118	031_S_4005	MCI
33	036_S_4894	AD	76	007_S_2394	MCI	119	031_S_4149	MCI
34	036_S_5063	AD	77	009_S_2208	MCI	120	031_S_4476	MCI
35	037_S_4001	AD	78	009_S_2381	MCI	121	031_S_4947	MCI
36	037_S_4770	AD	79	009_S_4530	MCI	122	036_S_2378	MCI
37	037_S_4879	AD	80	009_S_4814	MCI	123	036_S_2380	MCI
38	053_S_5070	AD	81	009_S_4958	MCI	124	037_S_4146	MCI
39	067_S_4728	AD	82	009_S_5000	MCI	125	037_S_4706	MCI
40	073_S_4853	AD	83	011_S_2274	MCI	126	041_S_5026	MCI
41	016_S_4195	AD	84	011_S_4235	MCI	127	053_S_2357	MCI
42	116_S_4338	AD	85	011_S_4547	MCI	128	053_S_2396	MCI
43	116_S_4625	AD	86	011_S_4893	MCI	129	053_S_4557	MCI

No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage	No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage	No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage
130	053_S_4661	MCIs	173	128_S_5066	MCIs	216	014_S_4079	MCic
131	053_S_4813	MCIs	174	130_S_2373	MCIs	217	014_S_4263	MCic
132	067_S_2195	MCIs	175	130_S_2391	MCIs	218	014_S_4668	MCic
133	067_S_2196	MCIs	176	130_S_2403	MCIs	219	016_S_4902	MCic
134	067_S_2301	MCIs	177	130_S_4405	MCIs	220	018_S_4889	MCic
135	067_S_2304	MCIs	178	130_S_4415	MCIs	221	019_S_4293	MCic
136	067_S_4054	MCIs	179	130_S_4417	MCIs	222	019_S_4548	MCic
137	067_S_4072	MCIs	180	130_S_4468	MCIs	223	020_S_4920	MCic
138	067_S_4184	MCIs	181	135_S_4281	MCIs	224	023_S_4034	MCic
139	067_S_4212	MCIs	182	035_S_4309	MCIs	225	023_S_4035	MCic
140	067_S_4310	MCIs	183	135_S_4356	MCIs	226	023_S_4115	MCic
141	073_S_2153	MCIs	184	137_S_4299	MCIs	227	023_S_4122	MCic
142	073_S_2182	MCIs	185	141_S_4160	MCIs	228	023_S_4243	MCic
143	073_S_2190	MCIs	186	153_S_2109	MCIs	229	023_S_4502	MCic
144	073_S_2191	MCIs	187	153_S_2148	MCIs	230	023_S_4796	MCic
145	073_S_2225	MCIs	188	153_S_4621	MCIs	231	024_S_4169	MCic
146	073_S_2264	MCIs	189	941_S_2060	MCIs	232	031_S_4029	MCic
147	073_S_4216	MCIs	190	941_S_4036	MCIs	233	031_S_4042	MCic
148	073_S_4259	MCIs	191	941_S_4420	MCIs	234	031_S_4194	MCic
149	073_S_4312	MCIs	192	941_S_4764	MCIs	235	031_S_4203	MCic
150	073_S_4360	MCIs	193	002_S_4171	MCic	236	031_S_4590	MCic
151	073_S_4443	MCIs	194	002_S_4219	MCic	237	031_S_4721	MCic
152	073_S_4614	MCIs	195	002_S_4229	MCic	238	036_S_4430	MCic
153	073_S_4825	MCIs	196	002_S_4251	MCic	239	036_S_4538	MCic
154	073_S_4986	MCIs	197	002_S_4521	MCic	240	036_S_4562	MCic
155	094_S_4434	MCIs	198	002_S_4654	MCic	241	036_S_4714	MCic
156	098_S_2079	MCIs	199	002_S_4746	MCic	242	036_S_4715	MCic
157	100_S_4512	MCIs	200	006_S_4346	MCic	243	036_S_4736	MCic
158	100_S_4556	MCIs	201	006_S_4363	MCic	244	036_S_4899	MCic
159	109_S_4594	MCIs	202	006_S_4515	MCic	245	037_S_4015	MCic
160	116_S_4175	MCIs	203	006_S_4713	MCic	246	037_S_4030	MCic
161	116_S_4199	MCIs	204	006_S_4960	MCic	247	037_S_4214	MCic
162	116_S_4635	MCIs	205	009_S_4324	MCic	248	037_S_4302	MCic
163	116_S_4898	MCIs	206	009_S_4359	MCic	249	037_S_4381	MCic
164	123_S_2055	MCIs	207	009_S_4543	MCic	250	037_S_4750	MCic
165	123_S_2363	MCIs	208	009_S_4741	MCic	251	067_S_4767	MCic
166	123_S_4127	MCIs	209	009_S_4903	MCic	252	067_S_4782	MCic
167	123_S_4780	MCIs	210	011_S_4366	MCic	253	067_S_4918	MCic
168	128_S_2002	MCIs	211	012_S_4094	MCic	254	070_S_4793	MCic
169	128_S_2036	MCIs	212	013_S_4395	MCic	255	073_S_4300	MCic
170	128_S_2045	MCIs	213	013_S_4595	MCic	256	073_S_4311	MCic
171	128_S_2123	MCIs	214	013_S_4985	MCic	257	073_S_4777	MCic
172	128_S_2130	MCIs	215	014_S_4058	MCic	258	109_S_4531	MCic

No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage	No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage	No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage
259	116_S_4167	MCIc	302	006_S_4150	HC	345	024_S_4084	HC
260	123_S_4096	MCIc	303	006_S_4357	HC	346	024_S_4158	HC
261	123_S_4170	MCIc	304	06_S_4449	HC	347	031_S_4021	HC
262	123_S_4806	MCIc	305	006_S_4485	HC	348	031_S_4032	HC
263	123_S_4904	MCIc	306	007_S_4488	HC	349	031_S_4218	HC
264	128_S_4636	MCIc	307	007_S_4516	HC	350	031_S_4474	HC
265	128_S_4653	MCIc	308	009_S_0751	HC	351	031_S_4496	HC
266	128_S_4671	MCIc	309	009_S_0842	HC	352	033_S_4176	HC
267	128_S_4842	MCIc	310	009_S_4337	HC	353	033_S_4177	HC
268	129_S_4287	MCIc	311	009_S_4388	HC	354	033_S_4179	HC
269	130_S_4250	MCIc	312	009_S_4612	HC	355	033_S_4505	HC
270	130_S_4294	MCIc	313	010_S_4345	HC	356	033_S_4508	HC
271	130_S_4542	MCIc	314	010_S_4442	HC	357	036_S_4389	HC
272	130_S_4605	MCIc	315	011_S_0021	HC	358	036_S_4491	HC
273	130_S_4817	MCIc	316	011_S_0023	HC	359	036_S_4878	HC
274	130_S_4925	MCIc	317	011_S_4075	HC	360	037_S_0303	HC
275	135_S_4406	MCIc	318	011_S_4105	HC	361	037_S_0454	HC
276	135_S_4489	MCIc	319	011_S_4120	HC	362	037_S_0467	HC
277	135_S_4689	MCIc	320	011_S_4222	HC	363	037_S_4028	HC
278	136_S_4189	MCIc	321	011_S_4278	HC	364	037_S_4071	HC
279	137_S_4303	MCIc	322	012_S_4026	HC	365	037_S_4308	HC
280	137_S_4596	MCIc	323	012_S_4643	HC	366	037_S_4410	HC
281	137_S_4631	MCIc	324	013_S_4579	HC	367	053_S_4578	HC
282	137_S_4815	MCIc	325	013_S_4580	HC	368	067_S_0056	HC
283	137_S_4852	MCIc	326	013_S_4616	HC	369	067_S_0059	HC
284	141_S_4423	MCIc	327	014_S_4080	HC	370	067_S_0257	HC
285	141_S_4426	MCIc	328	014_S_4093	HC	371	070_S_4856	HC
286	141_S_4711	MCIc	329	014_S_4401	HC	372	070_S_5040	HC
287	141_S_4976	MCIc	330	014_S_4576	HC	373	073_S_0089	HC
288	153_S_4077	MCIc	331	014_S_4577	HC	374	073_S_0311	HC
289	941_S_4187	MCIc	332	016_S_4121	HC	375	073_S_4155	HC
290	941_S_4377	MCIc	333	016_S_4951	HC	376	073_S_4382	HC
291	002_S_0295	HC	334	016_S_4952	HC	377	073_S_4393	HC
292	002_S_0413	HC	335	018_S_4257	HC	378	073_S_4552	HC
293	002_S_0685	HC	336	018_S_4313	HC	379	073_S_4559	HC
294	002_S_1261	HC	337	018_S_4349	HC	380	073_S_4739	HC
295	002_S_1280	HC	338	018_S_4399	HC	381	073_S_4762	HC
296	002_S_4213	HC	339	018_S_4400	HC	382	073_S_4795	HC
297	002_S_4225	HC	340	019_S_4367	HC	383	073_S_5023	HC
298	002_S_4262	HC	341	019_S_4835	HC	384	094_S_4234	HC
299	002_S_4270	HC	342	023_S_4020	HC	385	094_S_4503	HC
300	006_S_0498	HC	343	023_S_4164	HC	386	100_S_0069	HC
301	006_S_0731	HC	344	023_S_4448	HC	387	100_S_1286	HC

No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage	No.	Subject ID	Clinical stage			
388	100_S_4469	HC	431	941_S_4255	HC			
389	109_S_4499	HC	432	941_S_4292	HC			
390	116_S_4010	HC	433	941_S_4365	HC			
391	116_S_4043	HC	434	941_S_4376	HC			
392	116_S_4092	HC						
393	116_S_4453	HC						
394	116_S_4483	HC						
395	116_S_4855	HC						
396	128_S_4586	HC						
397	128_S_4599	HC						
398	128_S_4607	HC						
399	128_S_4609	HC						
400	128_S_4832	HC						
401	129_S_0778	HC						
402	129_S_4369	HC						
403	129_S_4371	HC						
404	129_S_4396	HC						
405	129_S_4422	HC						
406	130_S_0969	HC						
407	130_S_4343	HC						
408	130_S_4352	HC						
409	135_S_4446	HC						
410	135_S_4566	HC						
411	135_S_4598	HC						
412	136_S_0186	HC						
413	136_S_4269	HC						
414	137_S_0301	HC						
415	137_S_0972	HC						
416	137_S_4466	HC						
417	137_S_4482	HC						
418	137_S_4520	HC						
419	137_S_4587	HC						
420	137_S_4632	HC						
421	141_S_0767	HC						
422	153_S_4125	HC						
423	153_S_4139	HC						
424	153_S_4151	HC						
425	153_S_4372	HC						
426	941_S_1194	HC						
427	41_S_1195	HC						
428	941_S_1202	HC						
429	941_S_1203	HC						
430	941_S_4100	HC						